

Pedagogical And Methodological Foundations For Developing Professional Thinking In Future Music Teachers

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Abstract: This article examines the role of methodological culture in the process of forming the professional thinking of future music teachers, highlighting its scientific, artistic, and pedagogical aspects. Issues of creative approach, methodological preparation, and the development of pedagogical thinking in modern music education are analyzed.

Keywords: music education, professional thinking, methodological culture, creative approach, pedagogy, methodology.

Introduction.

One of the most important issues today is the problem of restructuring the professional thinking of future music teachers. This involves activating a personal and value-based attitude toward the methodological aspects of future specialists' professional activities and creating the most favorable conditions to stimulate interest in the process of methodological preparation.

Depending on the level of equipment of a specific audience from the standpoint of the methodology of teaching music, the teacher chooses a particular logic for presenting the problem and methods of pedagogical encouragement to stimulate students' creative activity during the learning process. In all cases, it is necessary to demonstrate that the future music teacher must strive to overcome stereotypes and formalism in thinking and achieve creative freedom. This makes it possible to identify objective and subjective reasons that hinder students' creative development.

At present, it is possible to move toward describing new ideas and approaches existing in the practice of general artistic and music education in higher education institutions. It should be emphasized that all of these are primarily connected with changes in the future teacher's approach to the educational and pedagogical process, as well as to the life of school and society. The future music teacher increasingly appears as a professional who is directly responsible for shaping moral and professional ideals, as well as for developing the artistic and musical needs and creative potential of future school students. These qualities are now more relevant than ever for the individual (including the student's personality), the nation, and society as a whole.

Such a task for the future music teacher can only be accomplished through an active-personal and individual-creative approach to teaching. The professional thinking of a future music teacher must be formed at a level that enables them to objectively and comprehensively evaluate proposed music-pedagogical concepts, curricula, and methodological recommendations. This is possible only through a deep

understanding of the social significance of professional activity, awareness of the relationship between music education and the didactic laws of the development of society, art, and pedagogical reality, as well as the ability to integrate various scientific and artistic knowledge with the needs of practice and the individual characteristics and capabilities of future students.

Main Part

To confirm the special importance of music in the life of students and society, it is useful to refer to the views of representatives from various fields of scientific and artistic practice, which also contributes to the accumulation of methodological experience. At the same time, attention should be paid to the multilevel yet holistic analyses conducted by these scholars in order to identify certain “problematic” issues in the fields of culture, art, and artistic (musical) pedagogy.

Another important fact should not escape students’ attention: the existence of diverse, and sometimes even contradictory, approaches to the specific issues of music pedagogy, including contemporary music curricula. It is necessary to encourage students to go beyond the methodological problems acknowledged by many authors and attempt to understand them from higher-level perspectives. This includes revealing the connections between specific problems of music pedagogy and processes of social transformation, the development of music education, and the relevant conclusions of general pedagogy. It should be emphasized that such a perspective on the problem gives the analysis a methodological character.

The named features of the first topic determine the essence of students’ mastery of the material. Above all, this process should be characterized by dialogical interaction between the teacher and students, as well as by methods that actively engage students in intellectual activity. The highest result is achieved not through memorization of facts, but through the emergence of each student’s own assumptions regarding the issues discussed in lectures, their desire to seek answers through independent work with literature and observation of musical and pedagogical reality. At the end of each lecture, the teacher sets a targeted perspective for the seminar, clarifies relevant questions, provides brief commentary on recommended works, and suggests the necessary literature for preparation.

The second topic, “The Content and Specific Features of the Methodological Experience of a Future Music Teacher,” logically continues the first and is based on students’ understanding of the urgency of restructuring the professional thinking of music teachers.

Starting with the interpretation of methodology as a general pedagogical doctrine, it is advisable to present other definitions of this concept as a scientific field possessing a system of theoretical knowledge and methods of scientific inquiry. Particular attention is given to the importance of a general philosophical approach in

the study and resolution of problems in specific scientific and artistic fields. Based on students' philosophical preparation, categories and laws of didactics can be examined in terms of their application in various areas of research practice, including music pedagogy.

When describing the distinctive features of general and specific methodologies, their interconnection should be highlighted, demonstrating the generalized nature and broad scope of knowledge transmission inherent in them. The issue of knowledge is among the most important when identifying the key aspects of general and specific methodology. During instruction, it is advisable for teachers to demonstrate examples of different approaches to analyzing a problem at both methodological and methodical levels.

The content, ideas, essence, and significance of methodological knowledge within the music pedagogy education system enable an examination of the problem of the future music teacher's methodological culture in accordance with the specific characteristics of their professional activity.

First, it should be noted that students of the bachelor's degree program in music education can be provided with a generalized understanding of methodological culture as an integral component of professional training. It is essential to consistently reveal the personal and professional qualities that characterize a sufficiently high level of methodological culture. The importance of methodological knowledge at various levels, which forms the basis of a holistic and conceptual approach to analyzing and solving professionally significant problems, should be emphasized.

Among the key components of a future music teacher's methodological culture are the ability to perceive pedagogical factors and phenomena, to anticipate their outcomes, and to scientifically justify the selection of various pedagogical influence tools.

The essence of the methodological culture of a music education bachelor's student can be examined at two levels:

- a) the future teacher's socio-political experience, including methodological knowledge, skills, and the need for their continuous improvement;
- b) as an integrative characteristic of the personality of a pedagogical music performer, manifested primarily in didactic thinking and creative knowledge, as well as in the transformation of musical-theoretical, pedagogical, and professional-performing theory into practice.

In improving students' methodological culture, the scientific and pedagogical style of thinking plays a decisive role. The thinking style of a future music teacher includes two interrelated aspects: scientific and artistic. While emphasizing their unity, it is necessary to give separate attention to each.

The scientific aspect of a professional music teacher's thinking is characterized

primarily by its role in understanding real facts, pedagogical reality, categories, and concepts that reflect laws and contradictions. In turn, the artistic aspect of thinking is manifested not only in observing and generalizing pedagogical reality, but also in the ability to provide individual and personal evaluation and interpretation.

The artistic orientation of the professional thinking of a music education student is determined primarily by the objective content of their activity—art itself (music) and the process that includes interaction between teacher, student, and music. This process predetermines the leading role of the artistic component in the professional thinking of the future music teacher.

During the study of this topic, special attention should be paid to developing students' value-based attitudes toward the problem of teaching professional musical-theoretical disciplines in general and toward the methodological level of their assimilation and transmission in particular.

When discussing the essence of methodological analysis of music pedagogy problems, it is recommended to begin by generalizing previously studied issues. It is important for the teacher to determine how deeply students have realized the necessity of studying the content of a specialized course and how their approach to the tasks and specific nature of a general secondary school teacher's activity has changed. If practical sessions are active, engaging, and convincing, the teacher should rely on students' opinions when introducing a new topic. If students demonstrate passivity, the teacher should independently summarize the material and carefully analyze the reasons for weak engagement.

Conclusion.

To change students' existing level of thinking, it is first necessary to resolve issues related to the optimal logic of presenting new material within the curriculum, determining the mechanisms for its generalization and the criteria for assessment. Clarity and coherence make it possible to present the material effectively to a given student audience.

Under such conditions, methodological analysis from the standpoint of the future music teacher's professional and creative activity becomes particularly engaging for students. Achieving this goal requires detailed explanation of the essence of methodological analysis at various levels. Typically, students come to understand the significance of each level for their own professional development and willingly assess their abilities and readiness to implement one or another level of analysis. The applied practical methods reinforce new material and logically lead to the need for identifying subsequent aspects of methodological analysis.

This process increasingly penetrates various spheres of human life, defines diverse areas of pedagogical science and practice, and enriches them with new content. Responding to the social demand for educating a creative individual actively involved

in understanding and transforming the surrounding world, pedagogy seeks to restore the prestige of individualized support activities.

To fulfill this task, modern pedagogy, including higher education pedagogy, must first establish solid methodological foundations. Special emphasis should be placed on the necessity of developing a high level of professional thinking among future specialists, fostering a broad conceptual approach, creative independence, and initiative in solving pedagogical problems. The realization of these goals is seen in creating special conditions that transition music education students from reproductive to creative learning. This transition can be achieved through targeted methodological preparation, which should be addressed not only within philosophical disciplines but also as a general pedagogical task.

Such preparation should be based on a specific model—a theoretical and methodological analogue that systematically reflects its structural and procedural aspects and their interrelations.

In conclusion, methodological culture is one of the key factors in shaping the professional thinking of future music teachers. The integration of methodological knowledge, creative activity, and personal approach enhances the effectiveness of music education. Therefore, special attention must be given to methodological preparation within the higher education process.

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